

Challenges in the representation of digital applications in SGAM: Overview and solutions

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Abstract—Digital applications foster innovation and spur new business models emergence in the power and energy sector, enabling further development towards smart grids. The ongoing integration of disruptive digital tools and smart grid solutions brings new complexities to the design of new smart grid applications. To cope with standardisation and interoperability concerns, the smart grid architecture model (SGAM) is the state of the art framework to design new applications in the ecosystem of smart grids. However, conceptual challenges related to the actors definition arise when mapping new digital applications to SGAM, among others such as artificial intelligence and digital twins.

Thus, this paper explores the latter challenges and presents three potential solutions to facilitate the deployment of digital applications in SGAM. These solutions are (i) the integration of a new interoperability layer to cover digital applications and humans in the current SGAM design, (ii) the decoupling of the component layer in three layers regarding the typology of actors, and (iii) the integration of a new interoperability layer to better represent the digital actors in cyber-physical applications.

Index Terms—Smart grids, digitalization, smart grid reference architecture model, SGAM, AI, cyber-physical applications

I. INTRODUCTION

The global demand for climate neutrality is forcing a holistic restructuring of the energy systems worldwide. As massive integration of renewables into the current power system is highly challenging, smart grids arise as a solution to cope with complex technical issues that hamper the system design [1].

Smart grids are power networks that unify information and communication technologies (ICT) and the electricity grid, allowing a bidirectional flow of information between network users as well as electricity between transmission and distribution grids in order to facilitate massive integration of renewable energy. This type of power networks requires transformation of the current system analysis, control, and communication to maintain system efficiency, reliability, and stability [2].

Within the smart grid context, digital technologies offer significant business potential. Although smart grid applications are already in use today, their design and possibilities have been further developed substantively during the recent years due to progressive advances in digital and cyber-physical technologies [3]. Such technologies may enhance a further digitalization of the energy sector, enabling the emergence of more complex solutions and applications [4].

Smart grids are considered a disruptive and positive innovation. Nevertheless, the complex interconnection of electricity and communication infrastructure, together with the penetration of new stakeholders and business models, hinders the deployment of new applications. These issues are identified as a problem of standardisation and interoperability related to the complexity of smart grids, which are considered as Systems-of-Systems [5].

In order to tackle the latter challenges, several architecture models have been proposed to facilitate the standard enhancement and application development. Examples of architectures are: the model defined by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) [6], the model envisioned by the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) [7], and the smart grid architecture model (SGAM) proposed by [8], in response to the European Commission's mandate M/490. In this context, SGAM is highlighted due to its intuitive structure and accessible use case management to cope with standardisation and interoperability. Currently, this architecture model has become the standard tool to facilitate the design of new smart grid applications (IEC SRD 63200:2021), including the interactions between the electricity sector, heating sector, and gas sector [9].

However, since the inception of SGAM, several modifications have been proposed to address technological changes related to upcoming digitalization trends. This is due to the broad definition of actors. SGAM describes actors as entities

that communicate, act, and interact. The description of actors was standardised and defined in [10], including examples such as people, software applications, systems, and databases.

Challenges arise when considering the diverse nature of actors defined currently in SGAM, being different for humans, hardware, and digital applications (e.g. artificial intelligence control algorithms). This different nature of actors is not considered explicitly in SGAM, as pointed out by [11], who highlighted the lack of differential consideration of emergent digital technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI), big data, cyber-physical systems (CPS) and distributed ledger technology. This finding is also shown in the EU Bridge project [12], where the importance of digital applications and data privacy is highlighted within the smart grids context. Furthermore, in [13], a modified version of SGAM was proposed to highlight the relevance of human decisions, separating human actors from the rest of entities reflected in SGAM. In addition, the approach shown by [14] describes the need of considering computational models within SGAM to achieve a coordinated view of issues such as control, optimization, and data analytics.

This paper identifies the challenges resulting from actors definition in SGAM. Likewise, in light of the relevance of this issue and the need of accommodating both digital applications and upcoming standards in SGAM, three extensions are proposed to provide a more comprehensive design of smart grid applications in line with current and future digitalization trends.

After the overview in the current Section, the SGAM model is presented in Section II, highlighting its limitations to cope with the diverse nature of actors such as humans, systems, and digital applications. Next, Section III proposes several adaptations of SGAM to overcome such barriers. Finally, conclusions are presented in Section IV.

II. SGAM APPLIED ON STATE OF THE ART SMART GRID APPLICATIONS

As a reference architecture, the main objective of SGAM is to facilitate the interoperable design of smart grid applications in different hierarchical levels of power system management. With this aim, SGAM is structured in a three-dimensional architecture, shown in Fig. 1. SGAM classifies the physical energy supply process into the domains of generation, transmission, distribution, distributed energy resources, and consumer premises. Subsequently, these domains are subdivided, depending on their spatial and data aggregation of the power system management, into hierarchical zones, creating a bi-dimensional model. The zones in SGAM are, in the order of increasing hierarchy level: process, field, station, operation, enterprise, and market.

Interoperability concerns are particularly significant when designing new smart grid applications in SGAM. Here, interoperability involves the way of transmit, exchange, and utilise information in order to contribute towards the achievement of several functionalities to fulfill a set of business objectives [15]. Such aspects are reflected in the five interoperability

layers, each of them are subdivided in regards of the different domains and zones [9]. These layers, which provide a three-dimensional perspective of smart grids, are further elaborated below:

- **Business layer:** reflects the regulatory and economic structures, policies, business models, business objectives, and business portfolios of market parties involved in the smart grid context. This layer supports decision-makers when defining new business capabilities, use cases, and business processes.
- **Function layer:** describes use cases and services, from an architectural perspective, provided by the smart grid application. Functions are independent from their implementations and actors involved.
- **Information layer:** identifies the information exchanged between actors, composed by canonical data models. This layer addresses the common information semantics for a comprehensive and interoperable communication.
- **Communication layer:** represents the protocols for the exchange of information between actors addressing the syntactic understanding of data structures.
- **Component layer:** describes the physical implementation of components participating in the smart grid context. This layer gathers actors such as systems, devices, power system equipment and infrastructure, which are identified in a certain domain and zone of SGAM.

Fig. 1. Representation of the SGAM [8].

Different challenges arise when developing new applications in SGAM as a result from actors definition. According to the most recent version of SGAM [9], there are different steps to map smart grid applications. The first step relies on the use case analysis following the required information defined in the standard IEC 62559-2 [16]. The process continues with the definition of the elements in the business layer, including business models, business objectives, business roles, and regulatory constraints. The sequence of next steps varies depending upon the nuances and scope of the specific use case.

On this basis, a top-down, bottom-up, or mixed approach may be followed when developing the remaining interoperability layers in SGAM. Following a top-down approach, the analysis continues with the definition of functions to achieve the business objectives. Then the information and communication protocols are identified. Finally, the component layer is defined and actors are mapped.

The above sequence of steps reveals one of the flaws of SGAM related to the diverse nature of actors. After the definition of the function layer, it should be pointed out that particular types of actors (i.e., digital applications, humans) are required to carry out the different functionalities to achieve the business objectives. Such actors have distinctive features regarding their ability to process information, add value to the data received (e.g., identify and classify patterns), and perform actions in an autonomous way. However, in SGAM, these actors are categorised in a general and standardised list which includes people, business roles, systems, devices, applications, power system equipment, control devices, network infrastructure, and computers [8].

In order to tackle this issue, an actors taxonomy was proposed in [17], where actors were divided in two categories covering actors to be mapped in the component layer (e.g. devices, applications) and actors to be defined in the business layer (e.g., operators, companies). A similar approach was carried out in the updated version of SGAM [9], which distinguishes between system roles and business roles. This, to describe the responsibilities of actors (e.g., people and software components) to achieve functionalities and satisfy a business process. However, the latter approaches may not either address the different nature of actors or facilitate the intuitive use case definition of digital applications.

Hence, the generalisation of actors in SGAM misrepresents the coexistence of active actors and passive actors. The active actors can be divided into two large categories of digital applications and humans where such actors are able to interact with the data and information and are able to make decisions, control, optimise, and provide value to information. Examples of active actors are SCADA systems, machine learning tools, AI algorithms, transmission operators, and maintenance personnel.

On the other hand, passive actors do not interact with the data acquired and rather are subjected to actions and commands coming from the active actors. The passive actors can be divided into two greater categories: power systems equipment and data acquisition and handling hardware. For instance, passive actors may be actuators, generator machines, transmission lines, electric vehicles, transformers, sensors, fiber optic cables, databases, and computers. Hence, the mix of actors of different nature may hamper the applicability of SGAM when defining digital applications and their interoperability with data handling hardware and power system equipment. Thus, to increase clarity and applicability of SGAM when addressing the above challenge, a new taxonomy of actors in SGAM, tailored to the different nature, is required.

This paper presents the new taxonomy in Fig. 2, where

the original pool of actors in SGAM may be decoupled in three different manners: (1) splitting passive actors (e.g., physical devices) and active actors in separated categories, (2) separating actors in components, digital applications (e.g., cyber systems), and humans, and (3) decoupling the pool of actors into physical elements (i.e., humans and physical components) and digital applications.

Fig. 2. Proposal for a more differentiated actor subdivision in SGAM.

Subsequently, to facilitate the deployment of the new taxonomy of actors in SGAM, different solutions to extend SGAM are proposed and discussed in Section III, highlighting their strengths and weaknesses.

III. PROPOSED SOLUTIONS FOR THE REPRESENTATION OF DIGITAL APPLICATIONS IN SGAM

A. Proposed extension of SGAM - intelligence layer

This solution proposes a new interoperability layer, the *intelligence layer*, to cope with the interoperability concerns arising from different approaches of active and intelligent actors (e.g., software tools, AI, hardware in the loop, control algorithms, humans) to add value through exploitation of the available information before fulfilling business related functions. The intelligence layer addresses the characteristics of the involved actors. In the intelligence layer, humans and digital applications process information obtained in the component layer, add value, and prepare the fulfillment of functionalities related to the business objectives. Thus, the intelligence layer enables a separation of the actors in line with the first approach presented in Fig. 2.

Likewise, this layer has strong interlinkages to the existing interoperability layers of SGAM. As represented in Fig. 3A, the intelligence layer is defined under the function layer in a lower interoperability level. This positioning is justified by the fact that emerging digital technologies are bringing new manners to achieve functionalities. Smart grid applications are evolving to more enhanced ways of controlling and analysing, where digital tools placed in the intelligence layer play a key role in enabling such functionalities.

Subsequently, humans and digital applications employ data objects and varied information (e.g., historical data, real-time data) contained in the information layer to add value and

(A) Intelligence layer.

(B) Decoupling of the component layer.

(C) Cyber layer and physical layer.

Fig. 3. Representation of the proposed modifications of SGAM.

perform actions towards a certain functionality, which justifies the placement of the intelligence layer above the information layer. Finally, the differences and interdependencies between component layer and the intelligence layer are particularly relevant. While digital applications and humans are placed in the intelligence layer, components, hardware, and power system equipment maintain their position in the component layer. In light of the above, the strengths and weaknesses of this solution are highlighted in the following lines:

Strengths:

- It represents the diverse nature of actors classifying into active (i.e., intelligent) and passive actors.
- It considers explicitly the deployment of digital applications in smart grids.
- It allows the definition of interoperability and communication standards between information objects, AI applications, and human interaction.

Weaknesses:

- It increases the complexity of SGAM, adding a new interoperability layer.
- It considers digital applications in the smart grid context. However, ICT providers usually spill over the domains of SGAM, offering their services to energy firms or providing software as a service products. Thus, this model may require further expansion to increase its plausibility.

B. Proposed extension of SGAM - decoupling the actors in three sub-layers.

The second solution to facilitate and clarify the development of new digital applications in SGAM is based on the division of the component layer into three sub-layers, as illustrated in Fig. 3B. The aim of this solution is to maintain the original design and simplicity in line with the objectives of the original SGAM designers [8]. Here, each one of these sub-layers hosts different types of actors to differentiate humans (component layer α) and digital applications (component layer β) from the rest of components and devices (component layer γ). The component sub-layers are organised horizontally according to the hierarchy of actors. The order α, β, γ represents the prominent role of humans as active actors and the lower hierarchy of passive components, including digital applications in the middle level of hierarchy.

Strengths:

- It provides a clearer definition of actors in SGAM, reflecting the diverse nature of digital applications, humans, and physical components.
- It follows the layers definition of the original SGAM as well as the adaption for cross sector domains.

Weaknesses:

- It does not consider the new interoperability concerns of digital applications in a special way.
- It places active actors in the same interoperability layer as passive actors.
- It does not follow the intuitive approach of the first solution (i.e., the intelligence layer), when following a top-down approach.

C. Proposed extension of SGAM - decoupling of the component layer between cyber layer and physical layer

Another possibility for the extension of SGAM is through the vertically decoupling of the component layer in two new layers that represent the cyber/digital actors and physical actors in a separated way. In this solution, the definition of CPS as entities that integrate embedded computing technologies into the physical world [4] illustrates their main hallmark: a dual nature. This nature is presented in Fig. 3C where CPS are represented with two new layers, the physical layer and the cyber layer, which host physical entities (e.g., humans, hardware, sensors and actuators) and cyber entities (e.g., software and cloud applications), respectively.

This solution generalises the definition of digital applications by means of separating their tangible and intangible parts. This may be exemplified by digital applications such as digital twins and cloud computing systems, whose hardware components are placed in the physical layer and software components and cloud applications are located in the cyber layer.

Strengths:

- It facilitates the proper mapping of CPS which would otherwise be placed at the original component layer, without highlighting their unique features.
- It represents the interoperability issues between the physical entities and the digital world.

Weaknesses:

- It does not follow the intuitive approach of the first solution (i.e., the intelligence layer), when following a top-down approach, considering humans as physical entities not different than physical components.
- It proposes an additional interoperability layer, as the first extension of SGAM, which may increase complexity of the original SGAM solution.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper has reviewed the challenges of deploying new digital applications in SGAM by highlighting existing issues resulting from actors definition. In order to overcome this issue, a new taxonomy of actors has been presented to clarify the diverse nature of digital applications, humans, and physical components. Furthermore, this study has tackled this issue by presenting three different extensions of SGAM. Such extensions facilitate the definition of the diverse actors in the model, while addressing the interoperability and standardisation concerns which arise from the deployment of new digital technologies. For future studies, the feasibility and applicability of each proposal should be addressed in a standardised way with the goal of revealing which extension offers the best solution to define current and future smart grid applications in SGAM.

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REFERENCES

- [1] X. Liang, "Emerging power quality challenges due to integration of renewable energy sources," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 53, pp. 855–866, 3 2017.
- [2] M. L. Tuballa and M. L. Abundo, "A review of the development of Smart Grid technologies," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 59, pp. 710–725, 2016. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.01.011>
- [3] E. Hossain, I. Khan, F. Un-Noor, S. S. Sikander, and M. S. H. Sunny, "Application of big data and machine learning in smart grid, and associated security concerns: A review," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 13 960–13 988, 2019.
- [4] X. Yu and Y. Xue, "Smart grids: A cyber-physical systems perspective," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 104, no. 5, pp. 1058–1070, 2016.
- [5] M. Usilar, S. Rohjans, C. Neureiter, F. P. Andren, J. Velasquez, C. Steinbrink, V. Efthymiou, G. Migliavacca, S. Horsmanheimo, H. Brunner, and T. I. Strasser, "Applying the smart grid architecture model for designing and validating system-of-systems in the power and energy domain: A European perspective," *Energies*, vol. 12, no. 2, 2019.
- [6] NIST, "NIST Framework and Roadmap for Smart Grid Interoperability Standards, 1.0," National Institute of Standards and Technology, Tech. Rep. 1108, 2010. [Online]. Available: https://www.nist.gov/system/files/documents/public_affairs/releases/smartgrid_interoperability_final.pdf
- [7] G. Simard, "Ieee grid vision 2050," *IEEE Grid Vision 2050*, pp. 1–93, 2013.
- [8] Smart Grid Coordination Group, "Smart Grid Reference Architecture," CEN-CENELEC-ETSI, Brussels, Tech. Rep., 2012. [Online]. Available: https://www.cenelec.eu/media/CEN-CENELEC/AreasOfWork/CEN-CENELEC_Topics/SmartGridsandMeters/SmartGrids/reference_architecture_smartgrids.pdf
- [9] IEC, "Systems Reference Document 63200:2021," 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://webstore.iec.ch/publication/62757>
- [10] CEN-CENELEC-ETSI Smart Grid Coordination Group, "Sustainable Processes," no. November, p. 101, 2012. [Online]. Available: http://ec.europa.eu/energy/gas_electricity/smartgrids/doc/xpert_group1_sustainable_processes.pdf
- [11] U. Cali, M. Kuzlu, M. Pipattanasomporn, J. Kempf, and L. Bai, "Introduction to the Digitalization of Power Systems and Markets," *Digitalization of Power Markets and Systems Using Energy Informatics*, pp. 1–16, 2021.
- [12] Data Management Working Group, "European energy data exchange reference architecture Data Management Working Group," European Commission, Tech. Rep., 2021. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/default/files/documents/bridge_wg_data_management_eu_reference_architecture_report_2020-2021.pdf
- [13] A. Szekeres and E. Snekkenes, *Representing Decision-Makers in SGAM-H: The Smart Grid Architecture Model Extended with the Human Layer*. Springer International Publishing, 2020, vol. 12419 LNCS, no. 248113. [Online]. Available: http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-62230-5_5
- [14] D. K. Panda and S. Das, "Smart grid architecture model for control, optimization and data analytics of future power networks with more renewable energy," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 301, p. 126877, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.126877>
- [15] GridWise® Architecture Council, "GridWise Interoperability Context-Setting Framework," Tech. Rep., 2008. [Online]. Available: https://www.gridwisecac.org/pdfs/interopframework_v1_1.pdf
- [16] IEC, "IEC 62559-2:2015: Use case methodology – Part 2: Definition of the Templates for Use Cases, Actor List and Requirements List," 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://webstore.iec.ch/publication/22349>
- [17] R. Santodomingo, M. Usilar, A. Goring, M. Gottschalk, L. Nordstrom, A. Saleem, and M. Chenine, "SGAM-based methodology to analyse Smart Grid solutions in DISCERN European research project," in *ENERGYCON 2014 - IEEE International Energy Conference*, no. May 2015, Dubrovnik, Croatia, 2014, pp. 751–758.